

Kinetics and Mechanism of Reaction Between Aniline and Red Fuming Nitric Acid: Part II.

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The kinetics of reaction between aniline and red fuming nitric acid has been investigated by a differential calorimetric technique. The reaction products have been examined by micro-analytical, chromatographic, U.V. and I.R. spectral studies. Some of the products of reactions are aniline nitrate, *p*-nitroaniline, nitroanilines, 2-4 dinitroaniline and nitrosobenzene. The reaction is first order with respect to both aniline and nitric acid. The rate constant is increased four times when ammonium metavanadate is added to the reaction mixture.

A plausible mechanism has been suggested. It appears that both oxidation and nitration of aniline occurs simultaneously.

In earlier communications^{1,2}, ignition studies of aniline and red fuming nitric acid (RFNA) propellants have been described. The kinetic study² was limited to the case of reaction with dilute RFNA. This was done to have moderate rate of reaction since the reaction is fast with concentrated acid. The study gives useful clues about the mechanism of combustion of aniline—RFNA propellants. However, it is difficult to extract much useful information about combustion reaction mechanism, since in the combustion reaction one of the reactants is concentrated RFNA and the reaction mechanism for diluted RFNA and concentrated RFNA may be quite different. Accordingly kinetic investigations with concentrated RFNA were undertaken. Since the reaction is quite fast, a differential calorimetric technique was adopted.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Materials*

(a) *Red-Fuming Nitric acid* : A.R. RFNA (Basic and Synthetic Chemicals, Calcutta) of density 1.486 gm/cm³ was used.

(b) *Aniline* : Commercial aniline (B.D.H.) was twice distilled over zinc dust to reduce the oxidation products, if any. The fraction distilling between 182–183° was collected. The density of purified sample was 1.022 gm/cm³.

(c) *Additives* : A.R. Ammonium meta vanadate was used as such without further purification.

1. R. P. Rastogi, H. L. Girdhar and N. L. Munjal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 301.
2. R. P. Rastogi and N. L. Munjal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 463.
3. R. P. Rastogi and K. Kishore, *Amer. Inst. Aeron. Astrn. (AIAA) J.*, 1966, 4, 1083.

(d) *Solvents for chromatographic analysis* : A.R. Benzene (B.D.H.) and absolute alcohol were used as solvents for chromatographic analysis. Absolute alcohol was dried over calcium chloride and distilled with sodium. Fraction distilling between 78–79° was collected.

(e) *Preparation of nitrating mixtures* : The nitrating mixtures⁴ viz., (HNO₃+BF₃), (HNO₃+HF), (HNO₃+oleum) were prepared by dissolving the gaseous BF₃ and HF in ice cold nitric acid. BF₃ was prepared by heating dry barium tetra fluoroborate at 500° and passed in nitric acid. HF was prepared by heating mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and calcium fluoride. Nitric acid was obtained from RFNA by passing slow stream of nitrogen to displace NO₂. The density of nitric acid was 1.4520 gm/cm³. Mixtures of nitric acid and oleum were prepared in a manner described earlier³.

2. Analysis of reaction products

(i) *Reaction between Aniline and RFNA* : The reaction was followed at temperature below 0° in order to avoid violent reaction. Aniline was taken in a beaker and RFNA was added drop by drop. When the reaction was complete, benzene was added to the reaction mixture. A white crystalline product (I) was separated and filtered. The compound decomposes above 190°. The U.V. spectra of this compound gives a sharp maximum at 212 mμ and a weak maximum at 285 mμ, the former signifying the presence of aromatic ring. I.R. spectra of the compound gives sharp bands at 2105 cm⁻¹, 2564 cm⁻¹ and in the region 2820–3040 cm⁻¹ correspond to the characteristic frequencies of NH₃⁺ group. Bands at 1623, 1235, 1527 cm⁻¹ correspond to the bending, rocking and stretching mode of vibrations of -NH₂ group. The band at 845 cm⁻¹ shows the C-N stretching. These spectral features show that the compound is aniline nitrate.

The filtrate was analysed in the following manner. It was distilled to remove excess of aniline and benzene. The coloured residue obtained after distillation was subjected to chromatographic analysis. Firstly, attempt was made to separate the constituents of the mixtures by paper chromatography but the mixture was found to be resolved into four coloured compounds, the bands for which were very close together. Thus, the separation and identification were difficult with paper chromatography. Thin layer chromatography using silica gel as the base and alcohol as the eluant was also not successful. Accordingly column chromatography was tried. The mixture was introduced in a 4' long alumina (Chromatographic grade E. Merck) column. A mixture of benzene and alcohol (95% benzene by volume) was used as solvent. Coloured compounds viz., yellow (II), orange (III), red (IV) and greenish blue (V) were eluted in the above order. Each fraction was further eluted over fresh alumina columns a good number of times. The components were identified by spectral measurements. The I.R. spectra was taken in nujol mull.

The spectra of compound (II) shows maxima at 228 mμ and 258 mμ in the U.V. region, which suggests that it is probably nitro-aniline. This is also confirmed by I.R. Spectra. Weak intensity peak in the region 3470–3320 cm⁻¹ correspond to -NH stretching frequency of amino group. In addition we get intense bands at 1563 cm⁻¹, 1351 cm⁻¹, 835 cm⁻¹. The nitro group produces two bands of high intensity one at 1563 cm⁻¹, which characterises

4. T. Urbanski, "Chemistry and Technology of Explosives", (vol. I), Pergamon Press, 1964, pp. 41-42.

the asymmetric vibration of the $\text{N} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{array}$ bond and another near 1351 cm^{-1} , which characterises the symmetric vibration of the nitro group. The band at 835 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-N stretching vibration. On the basis of these facts it appears that the compound is nitro-aniline.

The spectra of the compound (III) was taken in visible region using absolute alcohol as solvent. A maxima is obtained at $560 \text{ m}\mu$. The U.V. Spectra in absolute alcohol shows a maxima at 219 and $258 \text{ m}\mu$. A weak maximum is obtained at about $3470\text{--}3320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shows the presence of the NH linkage of the amino group. The bands at about 1540 cm^{-1} and 1350 cm^{-1} correspond to the characteristic asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of NO_2 group. The visible, U.V. and I.R. spectra taken together confirms that compound (III) is 2-4 dinitro aniline.

Compound (IV) gives a broad maximum at $500\text{--}510 \text{ m}\mu$ in the visible region. In U.V. region it gives weak maxima at $216 \text{ m}\mu$, $238 \text{ m}\mu$ and $256 \text{ m}\mu$ and strong maximum at $350 \text{ m}\mu$. The I.R. spectra gives bands at 1555 cm^{-1} , $1380\text{--}1250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 3040 cm^{-1} and $1600\text{--}1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at 1555 cm^{-1} shows the presence of azo group ($-\text{N} = \text{N}-$). The bands between $1600\text{--}1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are accounted for aromatic C-H vibrations. Two bands between $1380\text{--}1250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to C-O stretching. The sharp band at 3040 cm^{-1} may be due to $-\text{OH}$ group or aromatic C-H stretching. The compound seems to be *p*-hydroxy-azobenzene.

Compound (V) gives maxima at $610 \text{ m}\mu$ in visible region. In U.V. region strong sharp maxima at $218 \text{ m}\mu$ and $300 \text{ m}\mu$ are obtained. The absorption at $218 \text{ m}\mu$ is due to the aromatic character of the compound. The absorption at $300 \text{ m}\mu$ and $610 \text{ m}\mu$ may be due to nitroso group. I.R. Spectra gives bands at $3470\text{--}3320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 1265 cm^{-1} and $830\text{--}810 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The weak maxima at $3470\text{--}3320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to N-H stretching frequency of amino group. The band at 1265 cm^{-1} shows the C-N stretching frequency and the band at $830\text{--}810 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ characterises the nitroso group. The above spectral results show that compound is *p*-nitroso aniline.

(ii) *Reaction between Aniline and N_2O_4* : NO_2 gas was passed in the ice-cold aniline in a slow stream for about half an hour. Excess of NO_2 from the reaction mixture was removed by heating it on a water bath. The reaction mixture thus obtained was subjected to steam distillation. The distillate was evaporated and allowed to crystallise. A golden yellow compound (VI) was obtained. The I.R. Spectra of this compound give bands at $3470\text{--}3320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 1570 cm^{-1} , 1335 cm^{-1} and some bands in the region $1600\text{--}1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bands at $3470\text{--}3320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to $-\text{NH}$ stretching frequency of amino group. The bands at 1570 cm^{-1} and 1335 cm^{-1} correspond to the nitro group. The compound may be nitro aniline.

(iii) *Reaction between Aniline nitrate and RFNA*: 2 gm. of pure aniline nitrate of particle size $150\text{--}200$ mesh was spread in a clean petri dish. A small drop of RFNA was added in the centre of aniline nitrate. A blue black speck appeared which grew in size in course of time. Around the periphery of the blue black product a green coloured product

was also formed. Within an hour the whole aniline nitrate turned green with blue black product in the centre. The two products were separated and washed with distilled water a number of times to ensure the removal of aniline nitrate. Micro-analysis of the green (VII) and blue-black (VIII) products conform to the molecular formula $C_6H_6NO_2$.

(iv) *Reaction between Aniline nitrate and N_2O_4* : NO_2 gas was passed over aniline nitrate. Aniline nitrate turned green and a blue black product is formed after some time. The green and blue black products were separated, and the micro-analysis was found to correspond to the molecular formula $C_6H_6NO_2$. Both the compounds give identical U.V. and I.R. Spectra. I.R. and U.V. Spectra does not give evidence of presence of any characteristic group. It may probably be nitrosobenzene.

3. *Ignition delay measurements with different nitrating mixtures*: Ignition delay has been measured by cup test¹ method taking 0.5 ml. of aniline in a porcelain dish. Varying amounts of nitric acid and other nitrating mixtures were added with a dropper and the time between the mixing and the instant when the flame appears has been measured with a stop watch. The results are plotted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

4. *Kinetic studies*.: The reaction between aniline and RFNA is fast and exothermic. Therefore, differential calorimetric technique was employed for kinetic measurements. Two identical pyrex glass cylindrical vessels (length 12 cm, diameter 6 cm and capacity 100 ml) were used as two cells. One of them was used as a reaction cell and other as reference cell. These were covered with rubber corks (protected by polythene sheets) having holes through

which stirrer and thermocouple could be inserted. A glass bulb containing one of the reactants was kept in the reaction cell. A mercury dipped heating coil was also inserted into this cell. The temperature difference in the two cells was measured with ten junction copper-constantan thermocouple enclosed in a glass tube and dipped in mercury. The output of the thermocouple was fed to a galvanometer through a potentiometer having lamp and scale arrangement.

In a typical run 40 ml of aniline was taken into each cell. Required amount of RFNA was introduced into the glass bulb when it was dipped in aniline in the cell. The contents of the cells were stirred vigorously by a mechanical stirrer and were allowed to attain the temperature of the thermostat. When thermal equilibrium was established as indicated by the stationary position of the galvanometer spot, the reaction was initiated by breaking the bulb containing RFNA in the reaction cell. A rise in temperature occurred due to heat released in the reaction. The galvanometer deflection was noted against various time intervals. The completion of the reaction was indicated by the return of the galvanometer spot to the original position.

When galvanometer deflection is plotted against time a typical curve of the type shown in Fig. 2 is obtained. Since deflection is proportional to the temperature difference ΔT_t ,

Fig. 2.

at any time t , the curve shows how ΔT_t changes with time. Simple procedure for evaluating rate constants from such a data are not available. However, it has been shown by Swinbourne⁵ that one can evaluate first order rate constant from the calorimetric data by

5. C. H. Weke, L. F. Beste and H. K. Hall, Jr., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 973.

using the following equation,

$$\Delta T_t + K \int_0^t \Delta T_t dt = e^{k_1 \tau} \left[\Delta T_{t+\tau} + K \int_0^{t+\tau} \Delta T_t dt \right] + C \quad \dots (1)$$

where

k_1 = first order rate constant

τ = fixed time interval

C = constant

T_t = temperature difference in the two cells at time t

$T_{t+\tau}$ = temperature difference in the two cells at time $t + \tau$

K = heat dissipation constant given by

and

$$\Delta T_t = \Delta T_i e^{-Kt} \quad \dots (2)$$

where ΔT_i is the initial temperature difference.

Equation (2) is obtained on integration of the following equation,

$$\frac{1}{C_p} \frac{dQ_d}{dt} = K \Delta T_t = - \frac{d \Delta T_t}{dt} \quad \dots (3)$$

where Q_d is the heat loss to surroundings and C_p is the specific heat of the reactants. ' K ' is expressed in min^{-1} . ' K ' would depend on the nature of the cell, stirrer and cell contents.

Fig. 3.

Since the deflection Δd_t is proportional to ΔT_t , we can replace ΔT_t by Δd_t without any loss of accuracy. It is easy to evaluate k_1 from equation (1) provided 'K' is known and the integrals can be evaluated. Equation (2) shows that the former can be evaluated by plotting $\log \Delta d_t$ against time in case suitable experimental data are available. Such data were obtained in heating the reaction cell containing the reaction products to the maximum temperature attained during the reaction. The subsequent fall in temperature was noted against time by recording the galvanometer deflection. A typical curve shown in Fig. 3 was obtained. When $\log \Delta d_t$ was plotted against time, a straight line was obtained and 'K' was obtained from the slope.

The integrals in equation (1) were obtained by estimating the areas under the curves when Δd_t was plotted against time. Thus, the quantities within brackets on both the left hand side and right hand side were evaluated. Next

$$[\Delta d_t + K \int_0^t \Delta d_t dt] \text{ was plotted against } [\Delta d_{t+\tau} + K \int_0^{t+\tau} \Delta d dt].$$

A straight line was obtained as shown in Fig. 4. This shows that the reaction is of first order. From the slope, the value of $ek_1\tau$ was estimated which in turn gives the value of k_1 . Following the above analytical procedure, k_1 was estimated at various temperatures and under different conditions. The results are given in Tables I and II and Figs. 2, 3 and 4.

RESULTS

TABLE I

Dependence of k_1 on temperature
 amount of aniline = 0.44 moles
 amount of RFNA = 9.5×10^{-4} moles

Temperature (°C)	k_1 (sec. ⁻¹)
30 ± 0.1	$1.0 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
35 ± 0.1	$2.6 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
40 ± 0.1	$5.2 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$

TABLE II

Effect of the amount of Ammonium metavanadate of k_1

amount of aniline = 0.44 moles

amount of RFNA = 9.5×10^{-4} moles. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

% of ammonium metavanadate in RFNA (w/v)	k_1 (sec. ⁻¹)
nil	$1.0 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
0.5	$4.2 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
1.0	$4.5 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
1.6	$4.8 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
2.5	$4.9 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
3.3	$5.0 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$

DISCUSSION

It is well known that the reaction between nitric acid and aniline is quite complex. Since RFNA acts both as an oxidising as well as nitrating agent on account of the presence of N_2O_4 , the reaction with aniline may give both the oxidation and nitration products. Therefore there is possibility of consecutive and side reactions. The species N_2O_4 and NO_2 would be in equilibrium and their relative proportion would vary with temperature. From the equilibrium data at different temperatures it can be shown that N_2O_4 is the principal reacting species at the experimental temperature.

In order to decide whether NO_2 or NO_2^+ is the more important species in the combustion reaction, ignition delay measurements for aniline+RFNA, aniline+(HNO_3+BF_3), aniline+(HNO_3+HF), aniline+($HNO_3+oleum$) were made. The data are plotted in Fig. 1. The result shows that the ignition delay and the ratio of amount of oxidiser and fuel (O/F) is minimum for aniline+RFNA. It appears that NO_2 plays a more significant role in the combustion of aniline.

Analysis of different reaction products shows that aniline nitrate, *p*-nitrosoaniline, nitro-aniline, 2-4, dinitro aniline and nitrosobenzene are possibly formed during reaction leading to combustion. The ignition delay experiments show that most of the compounds ignite easily with RFNA.

Amongst the reaction products formed in the reaction between aniline nitrate and RFNA it was possible to isolate green (VII) and blue black (VIII) products. On the basis of I.R. Spectra it appears that these are probably nitroso compounds. The spectra also gives indication that these do not possess aromatic character. Microanalysis of the com-

pounds corresponds to $(C_6H_6NO_2)_x$. It may be noted that correspond to

molecular formula $C_6H_5NO_2$. The latter conforms to the spectral characteristics of the

compounds (VII) and (VIII). It appears therefore, that may be at least one of the

products of the reaction. Among the oxidation products of aniline, quinone and amino phenol ignite spontaneously with RFNA. But these products could not be identified in the reaction mixture. It appears that both sequences of the reactions involving oxidation⁶ and nitration^{7,8} are involved during ignition leading to combustion. A plausible mechanism is given below :

The kinetic data shows that the reaction is first order with respect to RFNA when aniline is in large excess. When RFNA is taken in excess the reaction is still found to be first order. The value of k_1 for different temperatures are given in Table I. The energy of activation was estimated by plotting $\log k_1$ against $1/T$. The activation energy was found to be 30 Kcals. The entropy of activation and free energy of activation are found to be 25 e.u. and 22 Kcals respectively. Influence of ammonium metavanadate on the rate constant for the reaction was investigated. Since ammonium metavanadate is known to act as ignition catalyst^{1,2} the kinetics of reaction in presence of ammonium metavanadate was studied. The reaction is still found to be first order with respect to RFNA. The rate

6. J. D. Roberts and M. C. Caserio, "Basic Principles of Organic Chemistry", W. A. Benjamin, New York, 1965, pp. 884.

7. E. D. Hughes and G. T. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2678.

8. J. H. Ridd, *Quarterly Reviews*, 1961, 418.

constant is found to be about four times greater than that without ammonium metavanadate. This shows that ammonium metavanadate acts as a catalyst. Further the rate constant is found to increase with the increase in the amount of ammonium metavanadate in RFNA showing thereby that ammonium metavanadate participates in the reaction in some fashion. However, the exact mechanism of the ammonium metavanadate catalysed reaction is difficult to specify at this stage.

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